

THE RATIONALE FOR SATURATION IN QUALITATIVE RESEARCH: WHEN PRACTICE INFORMS THEORY

Review
Article

Keywords

Qualitative Research;
Data Saturation;
Sampling;
Scientific Rigor;

Abstract

This paper acknowledges the significance of data saturation in research as a methodological instrument governing the non-negotiable yet highly questioned scientific rigor in research. Therefore, it employs a reflective research-practice based approach to evaluate the importance of data saturation in qualitative research. It draws on context and time-bound first-hand research practices of sampling and collecting quality data using face-to-face, semi-structured interviews with migrant entrepreneurs in London between 2017-2021. This paper shows that data saturation is a complex phenomenon expanding beyond the theoretical rationale experienced as a before, during and after an iterative and reflective process of engaging with the research participants and data (i.e., triangulation of sources, disciplinary traditions, researcher's experiences and participants' willingness and readiness to share), which anchors researcher's decision to resume data collection. This paper employs reflective fieldwork-based practices to demonstrate how saturation is reached in a phenomenological interpretative study. Thus, it contributes to the qualitative research scholarship by addressing the misalignment between theory and practice and bringing a practice-based, triangulated perspective on data saturation.

INTRODUCTION

The research participants and their experiences, expressed either numerically or linguistically, reside at the heart of the research. As such, qualitative and quantitative researchers need to think carefully and reflect deeply on their sample. Therefore, the researchers are responsible for rigor throughout the research process, and when they sample, they need to consider the inclusion criterion and the sample size (Hennink, Kaiser, & Marconi, 2017; Hennink, Kaiser, & Weber, 2019; Saunders, Sim, Kingstone, Baker, Waterfield, Bartlam, Burroughs, & Jinks, 2018).

To ensure scientific rigor through the appropriateness of the sample size, qualitative researchers have designed models and practice-based principles to estimate and assess the likely number of interviews needed to reach data saturation for any given study (Morse, 2015; 2020; Saunders et al., 2018). Filling the need for a gold standard to inform sample size and scientific rigor, researchers across different disciplinary fields, defined data saturation as a “guarantor of qualitative rigor” (Morse, 2015, p. 587), the point of “diminishing returns” (Rowlands, Waddell, & McKenna, 2016, p. 40); the moment when “information power” is reached (Malterud, Siersma, & Guassora, 2016, p. 2); a point when new information becomes problematic, faulty and out of scope (Low, 2019) and the phase when no additional themes and insightful information emerge from the collected data (Hennink et al., 2019).

Paradoxically, despite becoming a standard research practice, data saturation remains fuzzy in its definition and how it operates due to its self-explanatory nature (Alam, 2020; Marshall, Cardon, Poddar, & Fontenot, 2013; Marshall, Baker, Lee, Jones, Lobo, & Brown, 2018). However, it becomes clear that despite its fuzziness, qualitative researchers increasingly use data saturation, whether oratorically or not, as the conceptual yardstick for assessing the sample size and as a guarantor of appropriate sample size, thus achieving scientific rigor (Braun & Clarke, 2019; Saunders et al., 2018; Sebele- Mpofu, 2020).

To ensure data saturation has been reached, and thus enough quality data has been collected and analyzed, some qualitative researchers have turned to quantitative statistical models (Guest, Namey & Chen, 2020) whilst others remained faithful to the qualitative research practices and triangulated different strategies. Therefore, at the forefront of the argument for data saturation in qualitative research is Mason’s meta-study (2010), which included over 500,000 PhD thesis and concluded that an average of 20–30 interviews is enough to reach data saturation. However, whilst these

perspectives may suffice in building a coherent argument, many of them are rhetorical arguments, not reflective of the researchers’ fieldwork experiences or the decisions to operationalize data saturation.

This paper acknowledges the significance of saturation in the argument for scientific rigor, which researchers must demonstrate as they pursue high-quality, ethical studies. Therefore, this paper does not intend to add to its conceptual fuzziness or challenge its theoretical models. Instead, it addresses the misalignment between theory and practice. Thus, it advances its methodological development by drawing on fieldwork research practices and aiming to demonstrate how the qualitative researcher decides and operationalizes saturation to ensure ethical and high-quality research practice.

To fulfil its aim, the remaining of the paper is structured as follows. First, to gain a deeper understanding of what data saturation means and its purpose in qualitative research, the following section presents an overview of the evolution of the key concept and relevant empirical evidence of applicable qualitative research practices reported by previous researchers. The next section is dedicated to fieldwork research practices and reflectively assesses data saturation practices experienced by the qualitative researcher when conducting face-to-face semi- interviews as part of a qualitative, phenomenological interpretative study. Finally, the conclusion reiterates this paper’s contribution to the qualitative research literature and practice and, in the light of its limitations, formulates future research directions.

EXPLAINING THE RATIONALE FOR DATA SATURATION IN QUALITATIVE RESEARCH

Grounded in Glaser and Strauss’s grounded theory (1967), the concept of “data saturation” evolved from the initial concept of “theoretical saturation” to become a critical methodological instrument across a wide range of qualitative research approaches (Guest et al., 2020). For example, in their inquiry to test theoretical models, Glaser and Strauss created this concept, stating: “The criterion for judging when to stop sampling the different groups pertinent to a category is its theoretical saturation. Saturation means that no additional data are being found whereby the sociologist can develop properties of the category. As he sees similar instances over and over again, the researcher becomes empirically confident that a category is saturated. He goes out of his way to look for groups that stretch diversity of data as far as possible, to ensure that saturation is based on the

widest possible range of data on the category.” (Glaser and Strauss, 1967, p. 61)

Over many decades, qualitative researchers have adopted and adapted its use across disciplinary borders and different qualitative approaches (Guest et al., 2020; Saunders et al., 2018; Saunders & Townsend, 2016). To respond to broader qualitative research approaches, the concept widens its spectrum of definitions, which all seem to agree that data saturation is that point in data collection when with any additional interview, no new or more in-depth information is provided (Saunders et al., 2018; Braun and Clarke, 2019). This same idea has been encompassed by researchers who associated data saturation with “diminishing returns” (Rowlands et al., 2016, p. 40); a point when new information becomes problematic, faulty and out of scope (Low, 2019); the moment when “information power” is reached (Malterud et al., 2016, p. 2); and the phase when no additional themes and insightful information emerges from the collected data (Hennink et al., 2019).

As the concept evolved, so did its methodological status, as it transformed from being an instrumental point in data collection to become a methodological “rule” (Sparkes, Duarte, Raphael, Denny, & Ashford, 2011), “a gold standard” in carrying out and reporting qualitative studies (Guest, Bunce and Johnson, 2006, p. 60) and more ambitiously inviting claims of “guarantee of qualitative rigour” (Morse, 2015: p. 587).

The concept’s modus operandi (Guest et al., 2020). Is adding to the complexity of this debate. After many decades, researchers are still divided on what is considered the correct number of interviews and thus the point of data saturation, when they can resume collecting data whilst still ensuring high standards and ethical studies (Morse, 2020). To contribute to this debate, Saunders and Townsend’s (2016) and Mason’s (2010) meta-studies showcased similar evidence suggesting that credible qualitative research includes between 15–60 interviewees.

Furthermore, adding to the complexity of this phenomenon is the fact that researchers have to submit an ethics committee application for approval before starting collecting data. Consequently, they have to estimate the sample size, and thus their study’s data saturation point, based on disciplinary tradition and previous empirical evidence, which is scarcely reported and highly contextual. Therefore, many build their sample size argument on a handful of meta-studies, specifically Saunders and Townsend’s (2016) meta-analysis of 798 articles published in 2003 and 2013 in ten top and second-tier academic journals and Masson’s (2010) who used a sample of over 500.000 published qualitative PhDs. The findings converge, reaching a consensus that either researcher provided no justification for participant

numbers in over half of the studies or that their arguments were rhetoric and purely theoretical instead of reflecting the fieldwork experience. Evidence suggests that researchers often choose to underreport their sample size and thus data saturation to avoid contradicting themselves and their ethical applications or because of the lack of operational clarity (Guest et al., 2020; Saunders et al., 2018; Sebele-Mpofu, 2020).

Despite the lack of consensus on what it means and how it should be operationalized, the importance of saturation in strengthening the scientific rigour in qualitative studies is increasingly recognized by many stakeholders, including researchers, institutional ethics committees and publishing boards (Robinson, 2014; Saunders & Townsend, 2016). As such, “data saturation” increasingly becomes an expected ethical and quality guarantor, accompanied by the researcher’s reflective acknowledgement regarding the selection of the research participants and appropriated depth of analysis to suit the outlined methodology. Consequently, researchers increasingly use it as an instrumental methodological tool to ensure transparent, ethical reporting and sound research practice (Saunders & Townsend, 2016; Saunders et al., 2018).

FIELDWORK PRACTICES OF TESTING FOR AND REACHING DATA SATURATION

Framed by this theoretical and empirical background, this paper aims to contribute to the qualitative research practice by reflectively reporting context-bound triangulated research practices in deciding the appropriate saturation point within a phenomenological interpretative study.

The qualitative researcher decided to resume data collection based on data saturation using a triangulation of sources and engaging iteratively, going back and forth between the aim of the study, the quality of data collected and the data analysis. All these steps are reflectively detailed in the following subsections.

Aligning aim – research approach-disciplinary tradition for a priori estimation of data saturation through sample size

The starting point for deciding the appropriateness of data saturation within any study is acknowledging its aim and methodological approach. Accordingly, the purpose phenomenological interpretative approach (IPA), which is the focus of this reflective methodological paper, is to gain an in-depth understanding of participants’ lived experiences of a phenomenon and increase the findings’ transferability to similar contexts and communities (Rajasinghe, 2019). This

paper acknowledges the claims made by renowned methodologists that “there is no right answer to the question of... sample size” (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2013:56). However, the researcher looked at the existent empirical evidence, suggesting that, as the phenomenological studies prioritize in-depth knowledge over quantity, most researchers seem to report reaching data saturation with 1-15 qualitative interviews (Bartholomew, Joy, Kang, & Brown, 2021).

Consequently, since the decision for the appropriateness of the sample size has been initially formulated a priori as part of the institutional ethics application, the researcher relied on disciplinary and phenomenological tradition and estimated the sample size and thus this study’s data saturation point. Specifically, this decision was based on the triangulation of the study’s aim (i.e., in-depth knowledge of lived experiences), the research approach (i.e., Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA)) and empirical evidence of disciplinary tradition (i.e. migrant entrepreneurship).

Triangulating these methodological sources, the phenomenological researcher estimated reaching data saturation with a sample of 20-30 interviews, as stated in the initial ethics committee application.

Triangulating hybrid forms of saturation

Following previous qualitative researchers’ footsteps, the phenomenological researcher acknowledges that the sample size does not suffice to claim data saturation (Hennink et al., 2017). Therefore, the researcher triangulates hybrid forms of saturation to build a credible argument for data saturation and reinforce the phenomenological aim of amplifying participants’ voices embedded in their lived experiences. Specifically, she goes back and forth between data collection and data analysis. Firstly, she pursues a priori thematic saturation by identifying the key research themes exemplified in the collected data (Guest et al., 2020; Morse, 2015). Secondly, she seeks inductive thematic saturation by identifying and coding new emergent themes in scope with the study’s aim (Constantinou, Georgiou, & Perdikogianni, 2017). Next, the researcher assesses data saturation as the point of diminishing returns with every extra interview she conducts and with every additional experience being shared by the interviewees by identifying convergent and divergent thematic and meaning patterns across interviews (Guest et al., 2020; Hennink et al., 2019).

From the situated research practice detailed above, data saturation is a complex, iterative process overlapping data collection and analysis. It is the ongoing assessment of the quality of the data collected and its embedded opportunity for in-depth, rich analysis instead of its outcome. Consequently, the data saturation decision can

often be altered throughout the research, and with it, the number of interviews will change as the researchers engage more with the data and revise the ideas formulated (Baker & Edwards, 2012; Morse, 2020).

These practices of data saturation can be operationalized either by calculating the “saturation ratio” (i.e. the number of new themes identified from a “run” of two interviews divided by the “base” number of “unique themes” or by identifying the key at the initial stage of interviewing) (Guest et al., 2020) or by actively but cautiously engaging in data analysis at the first stages of interviewing to identify and interpret contextual meanings (Braun and Clarke, 2019), whilst managing the risk of “silencing” new emergent, relevant themes (Morse, 2020).

Assessing the researcher’s skills and participants’ willingness to share their experiences

The scholarship on data saturation focuses almost exclusively on research practices and strategies, underplaying the importance of researchers’ insider-outsider positionality, research and interviewing skills (i.e., communication, data analysis) and participants’ knowledge and willingness to share their experiences in a study.

Specifically, a skilful and experienced qualitative researcher might be able to motivate participants to share richer personal experiences and might have the analytical skills to capture deeper meaning from a smaller sample than a more inexperienced one. Similarly, the sampling techniques used and the shared cultural or professional background with the potential participants might ease the opportunity to build trust and rapport between the researcher and participants, which creates the opportunity for richer and more personal experiences to be shared by participants during interviews (Chitac & Knowles, 2019). The above arguments show that it is challenging to predict the articulateness of participants, the impact of power asymmetries during data collection and thus the a priori quality of the data. Additionally, researchers’ skills play an equally critical role in determining what sample size suffices to reach data saturation whilst adequately managing the risk of bias interpretation and sampling (Guest et al., 2020; Sebele-Mpofu, 2020).

In the context of this study, the researcher was a cultural insider to the researched community and experienced in professional interviewing and data analysis, although still an early-career researcher on a full-time learning journey. This allowed her to engage the participants and inspire them to share their lived experiences and to reach data saturation based on 18 interviews with women entrepreneurs and 31 men entrepreneurs, which is in line with the tradition of qualitative research within the field of

migrant entrepreneurship (Lasalle and Shaw, 2021; Vershinina, Rodgers, Mcadam, & Clinton, 2019; Villares and Essers, 2019).

Triangulating all the data saturation strategies detailed above, the qualitative researcher iteratively grew the sample size from the a priori estimated sample of 20-30 included in the ethics application to 49 participants (18 women and 31 men). This was mainly due to the new gendered perspective that emerged during data analysis, which motivated the researcher to continue collecting data to achieve data saturation.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper sheds light on qualitative researchers' opportunities and challenges when pursuing high-quality studies. It employs context-bound research practices to demonstrate how data saturation can be reached in a qualitative, phenomenological study with a sample of 49 interviewees (18 women and 31 men).

Consequently, reflecting on how researchers try to ensure the appropriateness of their sample size and build a credible argument for data saturation as their guarantor of quality, this study demonstrates that data saturation is not a one-size-fits-all process. Instead, it proves that data saturation is a complex process that requires diligent, iterative assessment of the data collection and analysis. It requires triangulating multiple saturation checks and practices, including a priori thematic saturation, inductive thematic saturation, and data saturation. Alongside these operational tools, researchers should assess the skills required to conduct engaging and trustful interviews, the competencies needed to support a proper data analysis and thus to understand and proactively engage throughout the research process. Therefore, despite its demonstrated significance in ethical and quality research practice and reporting, researchers should go beyond the routine of ticking the box. Still, they should seek data saturation whilst considering a variety of quality considerations during data collection, such as selection bias, participants' characteristics, the opportunity for co-creation and the overall quality of data collected.

Furthermore, the researcher explained that saturation plays a significant role in providing methodological justification and clarity of reasoning (Sim, Saunders, Waterfield, & Kingstone, 2018). However, it also exposed the risks of compromising the credibility and validity of qualitative studies and researchers' legitimacy when the research process is underreported or lacks transparency and rationale of sample sizes and underlying assumptions. Unfortunately, many qualitative researchers continue to underreport these methodological practices, as they leave many

“how” and “when” questions unanswered (Malterud et al., 2016).

By addressing this methodological gap, this article reinforces the need for more qualitative researchers to report their research practices with more transparency and diligence and thus support the qualitative methodological development. It is essential to acknowledge that data saturation, as is the case of many other qualitative methods, “is not the number of cases that matters, it is what you do with them.” (Emmel, 2013, p. 154)

The paper aims to contribute more ambitiously to the formalization of justifiable qualitative research methods. Specifically, it addresses the misalignment between theory and practice, supporting Giorgi's perspective that “a method should be clear such that it is useable by any researcher.” Of course, this is not to say that all qualitative or phenomenological studies should look the same. Instead, researchers can turn to these context-bound research practices as a source of greater scientific clarity when they need to justify and thus defend the quality of their qualitative studies.

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